

PYTHONDA DASTUR KODINI YOZISH

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301 – MI guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7925009>

Anotatsiya: Python interpreteri skriptli til bo'lib, kodni bajarish uchun kompilyatorga muhtoj emas. Python kodini yozish uchun turli IDE (Integrated Development Environment) va mant muharrirlaridan foydalanish mumkin. Pythonda kod yozishda probellar va satr tashlashlar orqali kodning tuzilishi belgilanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: python, print, def, for, in, input

Python tilida dastur instruktsiyalar to'plamidan tashkil topgan bo'lib, har bir instruktsiya alohida qatorda joylashgan bo'lishi kerak bo'ladi. Masalan:

```
print(3 + 5)
print("Python – dasturlash tili!")
```

Python da xat boshi (otstup) juda muhim ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. xat boshining noto'g'ri joylashtirilishi dasturda xatolikka olib keladi. Masalan yuqoridagi dastur kodini quyidagicha yozamiz:

```
print(3 + 5)
print("Python – dasturlash tili!")
```

Ushbu dastur kodi yuqoridagisi bilan bir xil bo'lishiga qaramasdan interpretator xatolik haqida xabar chiqaradi va dastur bajarilmaydi. Shuning uchun ham Pythonda har bir instruktsiya alohida qatorda yozilishi shart. Ushbu hususiyat Pythonning boshqa tillardan, masalan, Java, C# tillaridan farqli jihatlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Shunga qaramasdan Python tilining ba'zi konstruktsiyalari bir necha qatorlarda yoziladi. Masalan *if* shart konstruktsiyasi shular jumlasidan:

```
if 10 < 20:
    print("Shart bajarildi")
```

Bu holatda 10 soni 20 sonidan kichik va "Shart bajarildi" so'zi chiqariladi. `print("Shart bajarildi")` instruktsiyasi oldida albatta xat boshi bo'lishi shart, chunki u alohida o'zi ishlatilmagan balki *if* shart konstruktsiyasining qismi sifatida qo'llanilgan. Odatda xat boshi 4 ga karrali probellar soni (4, 8,12) bilan yozish kelishilgan, lekin probellar soni 5 va undan ortiq bo'lsa ham dastur ishlaydi.

Registrga sezuvchanlik. Python – registrga sezuvchan til hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun *print*, *Print* yoki *PRINT* ifodalar turli ifodalarni anglatadi. Agarda *print* berilganlarni chiqarish ifodasi o'rniga *Print* ishlatilsa xatolik yuz berganligini ifodalovchi " *name* „*Print' is not defined*“ shaklidagi xabar chiqadi.

Kommentariyalar (Izohlar). Pythonda u yoki bu dastur kodlari qismlari nima ish qilishini qayd qilib ketish uchun izohlardan foydalaniladi. Interpretator dasturni baytkodga tarjima qilayotganda yoki bajarayotganda izohlarni e'tiborsiz qoldiradi. Shuning uchun izohga olingan berilganlar dastur ishlashiga hech qanday ta'sir ko'rsatmaydi.

Python dasturlash tilida izoh qo'yish uchun “#” belgisidan foydalaniladi. Odatda izohlar blokli va satrli izohlarga ajratiladi. Lekin har ikkalasi ham “#” belgisi orqali hosil qilinadi. Farqi satr izohlar dastur kodi yozilgan qatorda koddan keyin yoziladi va u shu satr nima ish bajarishi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlardan tashkil topadi, ya'ni:

```
print("Shart bajarildi") # xabarni konsolga chiqarish
```

Blokli izohlar esa dasturning biror qismi nima ish bajarishi yoki shu qism mazmunini foydalanuvchiga qisqacha ochib berish uchun ishlatilib, dasturni shu qismi kodlaridan oldin alohida satr yoki satrlarda “#” va bitta probel bilan yoziladi, masalan:

```
# ushbu funksiya 1 dan n gacha bo'lgan butun sonlarning # yigindisini hisoblaydi
def Summa(n):
3   s=0
   for a in range(1,n+1):
       s = s + a
7
8   print(a, " ",s)
9   return s
```

Asosiy funksiyalar. Python o'z ichiga bir necha ichki funksiyalarni qamrab olgan. Ularni ba'zilar dasturlash jarayonida, ayniqsa dasturlash sistaksisini o'rganish paytida juda ko'p qo'llanilganligi sababli ularni alohida qarab chiqamiz.

Ma'lumotni konsol ekraniga chiqarish – *print()* funksiyasi hisoblanadi. Funksiyaga argument sifatida konsolga chiqariluvchi qiymatlar (satr, son, ifoda va x.k.) berilishi mumkin:

```
print("Hello python!")
```

Agarda birdaniga bir nechta qiymatlarni chop etish talab qilinsa, u holda ularni *print()* funksiyasiga “,” bilan ajratib kiritiladi:

```
print("F.I.SH.:", "Eshmatov", "Toshmat")
```

Natijada ular ekranga probel bilan ajratilgan holatda chop etiladi. *F.I.O: Eshmatov Toshmat*

Agarda *print()* funksiyasi ma'lumotlarni chop qilish uchun mo'ljallangan bo'lsa, *input()* ekrandan berilganlarni kiritish uchun qo'llaniladi. *input()* funksiyasiga argument sifatida biror bir satr berilishi mumkin. Ushbu satr konsol ekranida aks ettirilib, kiritilishi kerak bo'lgan berilganlar uchun yordamchi taklif vazifasini bajaradi. Masalan:

```
name = input("F.I.O.: ")
print("Salom", name)
```

Natijaning konsol ekranidagi ko'rinishi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

F.I.O.: Eshmatov Toshmat Salom Eshmatov Toshmat

Xulosa

Pythonda dastur kodini yozish uchun Python interpreterini o'rnatish, IDE yoki mant muharriridan foydalanish, Python sintaksisiga rioya qilish, turli dasturlash paradigmatlari va tushunchalarini ishlatish, xatoliklarni oldini olish va boshqarish, kommentariyalar va

dokumentatsiyalar yozish kerak. Pythonda dastur kodini yozish sodda va samarali bo'lib, turli sohalarda ilovalar yaratishga imkon beradi.

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